

Takrarishta – Pharmaceutical Preparation and an Approach to Regard it as an Ayurvedic Probiotic in view of Ancient Literature

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda is an ancient healing science and various medicines and formulations are described under this. The world health organization (WHO) has defined probiotics as, “Live microorganisms, which when administered in adequate amounts confer health benefits on the host”. Sandhan Kalpana (fermentation process) is a unique form in which acidic and alcoholic fermented drugs are prepared. These drugs were called Asavarishta and are used in various diseases related to gastrointestinal disorders and other diseases as mentioned in Charak and Sushruta Samhitas. In the present study, Takrarishta that come under Asavarishta kalpana, can be considered as an ayurvedic probiotic based on the ancient literature and therapeutic uses.

Keywords: Probiotic, Fermentation, Asava, Arishta, Takrarishta.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda is an ancient healing science and various medicines and formulations are described under this. *Sandhan Kalpana* (biomedical fermented formulation) is one of the best dosage forms of *Ayurveda* in practice in the last thousand years. Various *Acharyas* have formed medicines under *Sandhan Kalpana* (fermentation process). *Sandhan Kalpana* is a unique form in which acidic and alcoholic fermented drugs are prepared. These drugs were called *Asavarishta* and as result of current findings of probiotic bacteria, these drugs are used in various diseases related to gastrointestinal disorders and other diseases as mentioned in *Charak and Sushruta Samhitas*.

United Nations World Health Organization, according to which probiotics are redefined as “live microorganisms which when administered in adequate amounts confer a health benefit on the host.” In relation to food the definition can be adjusted by emphasizing that the beneficial effect is exerted by the

microorganisms “when consumed in adequate amounts as part of food.”¹

Several bacterial genera are used in probiotic preparations, including; *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, *Enterococcus*, *Escherichia*, *Streptococcus* and *Bacillus*. Along with this, certain fungal strains such as *Saccharomyces* are also used for probiotic application². Though probiotic bacteria are generally a component of healthy microbiota and confers normal health status, their reduction/absence under disease conditions needs their administration into dysbiotic microbiota in order to provide health benefits.

The probiotics naturally present in certain food products or certain medicinal formulations can be used as probiotic supplements in order to provide benefits in dysbiotic microbiota. These microorganisms are naturally present in several fermented food products. Such as *LAB* and *Streptococcus thermophilus* which are present in *yoghurt*.³

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The range of food products containing probiotic property is wide and still growing. The main products existing in the market are dairy-based ones including fermented milks, cheese, ice cream, buttermilk, milk powder, and yogurts, the latter accounting for the largest share of sales⁴. Non-dairy food applications include soya based products, nutrition bars, cereals, and a variety of juices as appropriate means of probiotic delivery to the consumer⁵.

Health Benefits of Probiotics

There is increasing evidence in favour of the claims of beneficial effects attributed to probiotics, including improvement of intestinal health, enhancement of the immune response, reduction of serum cholesterol, and cancer prevention. These health properties are strain specific and are impacted by the various mechanisms mentioned above. While some of the health benefits are well documented others require additional studies in order to be established. In fact, there is substantial evidence to support probiotic use in the treatment of acute diarrhoeal diseases, prevention of antibiotic-associated diarrhoea, and improvement of lactose metabolism, but there is insufficient evidence to recommend them for use in other clinical conditions.

Probiotics influence the intestinal microbiota, enhance the synthesis of short-chain fatty acids (SCFA), and reduce the chance of developing diseases⁶. Probiotics minimize the risk of several diseases, such as constipation, colon cancer, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and obesity, and they treat a range of intestinal disorders, including inflammatory bowel disease, among others⁷.

Fermentation is a process of preparing formulations wherein the therapeutic attributes of a group of ingredients are extracted from *swarasa* (freshly extracted juice of plants) or *kwatha*

(decoction prepared in water) with the help of biochemical or microbial fermentation and

anaerobic respiration into the liquid, these formulations are called *Asavarishta*⁸.

In the present study, *Takrarishta* that come under *Asavarishta kalpana*, can be considered as an *ayurvedic* probiotic and is evaluated for its probiotic

properties as is mentioned by *Charaka* in *Grahanidosha Chikitsa Adhyaya*.

Takrarishta is 1st mentioned in *Charak Samhita* under *Grahani Roga Adhikaara*⁹. This is indicated in *Gulma, Arsha, Shotha, krimi, Medoroga* and *Udara rogas* and the same is mentioned in *AFI*¹⁰

In *Takrarishta*, *Takra* is used as *Dravadravya* hence it is called as *Takrarishta*. *Takra* is *Apakwa Rasa* and method of preparation as like of *Asava Kalpana* only even though it is called as *Takrarishta* not as *Takrasava* because it is exceptional formulation in *Asava Kalpana*. In *AFI* *Takrarishta* is mentioned as per reference of *Charaka Samhita Grahani Chikitsa Adhikara* and dose have mentioned it as 12ml to 24ml *BD*¹⁰.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Aim- To perform pharmaceutical preparation of *Takrarishta* and correlate it with ancient literature to study its presumptive probiotic properties.

1. Wide mouthed vessels/ jars made up of glass.
2. Spatula with long handle.
3. A clean cloth(muslin cloth) for filtering
4. Clay and cotton cloth for covering.
5. Electric weighing machine for measuring weights.
6. Clean glass jars for storage of prepared medicine (samples)

Takrarishta preparation (Reference - *Charak Samhita; grahini rogadohikar*)

Date of starting	1 June 2024
Date of completion	21 June 2024

Equipments:

Glass jar (40 centimeter length ,15 centimeter diameter-mouth , 5 liters capacity), cotton cloth, spatula, grinder etc.

Table showing ingredients of *Takrarishta*

Sr. no.	Ingredients	Botanical name	Parts used	Quantity in grams
1	<i>Yavani</i>	Trachyspermum ammi	Fruit	144 grams
2	<i>Amlaki</i>	Phyllanthus emblica	Fruit	144 grams
3	<i>Haritaki</i>	Terminalia chebula	Fruit	144 grams
4	<i>Maricha</i>	Piper nigrum	Fruit	144 grams
5	<i>Saindhava Lavana</i>	Sodium chloride	Lavan	48 grams
6	<i>Vida Lavana</i>	ammonium chloride	Lavan	48 grams
7	<i>Samudra Lavana</i>	Sodi muris	Lavan	48 grams
8	<i>Sauvarchala Lavana</i>	Unaqua Sodium Chloride	Lavan	48 grams
9	<i>Romaka Lavana</i>	Sodium chloride	Lavan	48 grams
10	<i>Takra</i>	Eng. Name -Buttermilk	-	3 liters

Pharmaceutical process of preparation of *Takrarishta* divided in three steps:

1. *Purav karama* – Authenticated raw drugs Collected in mentioned quantity. *Takra* is prepared according to Susruta Samhita as mentioned in AFI Part¹¹ -1. It is the liquid obtained by adding equal quantity of water to curd (*dadhi*) and decanting the butter by churning.

2. *Pradhan karma* – Mix all ingredients into *takra* and poured the mixture in glass jar. Then covered the lid of the jar and left it undisturbed for fermentation.

3. *Pashchat Karma*: When fermentation gets complete and test get done, filter it and leave for few days to allow the sediments to settle down at the bottom and again filtered to separate the sediments and preserve it.

Procedure of Preparation

General procedure followed for the preparation of *Takrarishta* as mentioned in AFI¹² is as follows –

- All ingredients are taken in above said quantity and made as fine powder individually. Preparation of *takra* is carried out by using *Dadhi* and Water quantity as mentioned in AFI¹¹ quantity. The *Dadhi* is prepared by traditional method. Cow's milk was procured from an authentic source, then it was boiled and cooled it to room temperature.
- In 3 lt. of cow's milk, 15ml of starter culture of curd was used as inoculum for making of *Dadhi*, then It is left undisturbed for one night. Next morning *dadhi* is ready for making buttermilk.
- Butter milk (*takra*) is prepared by mixing the curd and water in 1:1 proportion. Then it is kept in churner and churned it for three hours till the separation of butter from the curd. After removing the butter, it is strained from a muslin cloth (no particle of butter should be left in it). All ingredients are taken in above said quantity and made as fine powder individually
- 3 liters of prepared *Takra* is taken in a vessel (glass container) and one fine powder of ingredients is taken along with stirring. After adding all ingredients that liquid of mixture is poured into fumigated glass jar, and closed properly. Then a clean cotton cloth with clay is wrapped around the mouth, for making it contamination free from the outside environment.
- The container is placed in the dark room without direct contact of air.
- Kept for Fermentation, Left it undisturbed, for few days.
- Keep observing onset and completion of fermentation changes.
- Once Fermentation gets complete open the seal and test get done, it is filtered and preserved.
- Around after 18 days, when sound stopped coming from jar, It is then opened it and performed the burning matchstick test, if the candle is blown-out it means fermentation process is still in process, packed it again and left

it undisturbed for some more days and opened on the 21th day.

10. Again, performed burning matchstick test. This time matchstick was continued burn it means there is no presence of carbon dioxide and fermentation process is completed. and we got all chief desired characteristics then dug out the porcelain jar and filtered it to obtained liquid.
11. The liquid is filtered from the sediments presents in its bottom with muslin cloth folded in four layers. It is kept at a safe place for next few days under observation
12. Sediments were there when it was seen after two days form the first filtration. It is again filtered for the 2nd time with muslin cloth folded in four layers, left it undisturbed for next few days. After two days, checked it again this time sediments were less and now filtered again for the 3rd time with the muslin cloth folded in four layers.

- After three filtrations, clear liquid is obtained. It is packed in transparent borosilicate jar and stored at cool and dark place, away from direct sunlight.

*Siddhi Lakshanas*¹³

- 1) No any sound in vessel.

2) When we blow a matchstick above the opening of vessel, flame doesn't go off.

3) Formation of specific color, taste and smell.

4) No precipitation in lime water. Fermentation is done in 21 days.

Observations - Procedure is followed in all the batches in *Grishm Ritu*.

1. Bubbling sound was coming start from 4th day.
2. Change in colour started observed from 3th day.
3. After making powder each Ingredient was taken as mentioned quantity.
4. On 18th day the sound coming from jar was stopped.
5. After adding all powder drugs to *Takra* total weight was 3. 816 kg.

Precautions

wide mouth vessel is needed to mix it well with spatula. Only 2/3 part of glass vessel filled with liquid mixture of all ingredients. The jar is left undisturbed during fermentation process and the is was prepared.

Table showing the percentage of loss as per volume and weight are presented.

Sample	Initial amount of <i>Takra</i>	Initial amount of mixture	Obtained amount <i>Takrarishta</i>	Loss in the amount of <i>Takra</i>	% of loss
<i>Takrarishta</i>	3 lit.	3.816 kg	1.530	1.47	49%

Takrarishta prepared with the same method, *Siddhi lakshana* for fermentation of *Takrarishta* attained between 16 to 18 days. In three filtrations by muslin cloth folded in four layers filtered *Takrarishta* obtained. Almost 49 % *Takra* is absorbed by raw

material, so the yield obtained is 50% of the total *Takra* that was added.

Day one 1st June ,2024

Observation on 6th June ,2024

Observation on 10th June ,2024

Observation on 18th June ,2024

Observation on 18th June ,2024

Flame Test

Ready for filtration

Filtered *Takrarishta*

After filtration, total 1.530 liters of *Takrarishta* is prepared out of 3 liters of *Takra* (buttermilk). Based on the literature, it is prepared by fermentation and is useful in gastro-intestinal disorders and thus, presumed to contain probiotic properties.

DISCUSSION

Sandhan Kalpana is a technique where the active constituents of the drug are incorporated into the acid and alcohol base to make the preparation therapeutically more potent. *Takrarishta* is mentioned in *Charak Samhita in Grahini Rogadhikara*. *Grahini* is digestive disorder, its main cause is *mandagni* and its symptoms are like irritable bowel syndrome (IBS). *Takrarishta* is fermented preparation of buttermilk and other herbal drugs. Herbal ingredients like *Amala*, *Haritaki*, *Yavani* and *Maricha* are used traditionally for gastrointestinal disorders. *Maricha* works as a bioavailability enhancer. *Lavanas* have *Rochaya*, *Bhedak*, *Deepak*, *Vatnashak* properties¹⁴.

Takrarishta (Fermented preparation) is advised in *Grahanidosha* (Irritable Bowel Syndrome) because all the ingredients present in *Takrarishta* are *Dipana* (carminative), *Pachana* (digestive), *Grahi* (bowel binding) in nature, *ushna veerya* and *madhur vipaki* and because of these guna, it neutralizes aggravated *pitta*, *amapachan*, *agnideepana*, *rochana*, *vatanulomana* and gives strength to *grahani*. *Takrarishta*, especially used in *grahani* caused due to aggravated *Kapha*. buttermilk is sour and astringent in taste and good for pacifying *Kapha*, and for stimulating *jatharagn* (digestive fire)¹⁵.

Buttermilk has characteristically sour taste. Increased activity of buttermilk is primarily due to lactic acid produced by Lactic acid bacteria; while fermenting lactose, the primary sugar in milk. The tartness of buttermilk is due to acid in the milk. As the bacteria produces lactic acid, the pH of the milk decreases and

case in, the primary milk protein, precipitates, causing the curdling or clabbering of milk. Buttermilk has probiotic qualities that help to regulate the functions of Gastrointestinal system¹⁶. *Takra* or butter-milk serves as a natural substitute for the probiotics. *Takrarishta* is more potent to buttermilk and also have probiotic properties.

Takrarishta exhibits a range of pharmacological actions through its unique composition. It acts as a *Tridoshagna* (harmonizing for all three *doshas*), *Deepaka* (enhancing digestive fire), *Paachaka* (aiding digestion) and *Srotoshodhaka* (purifying the channels). These actions work together to tackle the core issues associated with *Grahani Roga*. By adding digestive efficiency, facilitating nutrient absorption, and minimizing discomfort associated with various gastrointestinal disturbances such as, diarrhea, flatulence and abdominal distension, *Takrarishta* serves as both a curative and preventive measure in digestive health¹⁷. It is act like a probiotic.

CONCLUSION

Takrarishta strengthens the digestive fire and promoting nutrition absorption. It alleviates gastrointestinal symptoms like diarrhoea, weakness, poor digestion, fluctuance etc. It acts like probiotic and improves gut health. *Takrarishta* is has been prepared by the fermentation process and is mentioned to be efficacious in treatment of gastrointestinal disorders and may qualify to be regarded as probiotic. However, due to lack of any microbial study, further microbial studies may be undertaken for the presence of probiotic microbiota in the required amounts as per WHO defining criteria for probiotics.

Declaration by Authors

Ethical Approval: Approved

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